

D 6.3- Report on pilot-tests of training materials and tools

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BEYOND Consortium

	ROLE	NAME	Acronym	Country
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3.	Partner	French Office for Research Integrity	OFIS	France
4.	Partner	French Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment	INRAE	France
5.	Partner	Oslo Metropolitan University	OsloMet	Norway
6.	Partner	Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK	TENK	Finland
7.	Partner	University of Central Lancashire-Cyprus	UCLanCY	Cyprus
8.	Partner	University of Helsinki	UH	Finland
9.	Partner	University of Humanistic Studies	UHS	The Netherlands
10.	Partner	University of Latvia	UL	Latvia
11.	Partner	University of Tartu	UTARTU	Estonia
12.	Partner	Stichting VUMC / The Embassy of Good Science	VUMC	The Netherlands
13.	AP	Trilateral Research LTD	TRI	UK
14.	AP	Heriot-Watt University	HWU	SCT

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1 Introduction

1.1 Abbreviations

RI	Research integrity
RE	Research ethics
RM	Research misconduct
FFP	Fabrication, falsification, plagiarism
QRPs	Questionable research practices
EC	European Commission
ECR	Early Career Researcher

1.2 About BEYOND

BEYOND is a research project that aims to promote research ethics and integrity (RE/RI) and prevent research misconduct (RM) by adopting a complex ecosystemic perspective on the issue. The project will explore the existing literature on behavioural ethics and moral psychology, as well as the socio-economic consequences of research misconduct, and engage all involved stakeholders in public consultation. To guide and equip all stakeholders in the research ecosystem, BEYOND will utilise this knowledge to develop psychologically informed contextual interventions and methodologies to measure the impact of RE/RI training materials, a best practice manual and guidelines, and new training materials and tools. The project will mobilise all stakeholders involved in the consortium and the stakeholder advisory board to ensure widespread dissemination of results and facilitate their institutional uptake and embedding. By reinforcing efforts to promote adherence to the highest standards of research ethics and integrity, BEYOND aims to contribute to public trust in science and support the development of a strong research culture that is conducive to ethical research practices.

The project aims to explore and advance individual and institutional responsibilities in promoting RE/RI and preventing RM. To achieve this goal, the consortium will develop measures that are co-created, needs- and case-based, streamlined, and based on best practices. These measures will be designed to engage, advise, and equip research-related stakeholders through guidance and educational instruments. By doing so, the project aims to contribute to the development of a research culture that is conducive to ethical and rigorous research practices and that fosters public trust in science.

1.3 About this deliverable

This deliverable describes the pilot-testing of the materials and tools developed under tasks T6.2 (*Devise a trainer guide to enhance training materials and tools developed by related projects*) and T6.3 (*Develop new training materials and tools on RE/RI*), and described in D 6.2 (*Report on supplementary trainer guide and new training materials on RE/RI*), ensuring that they are practical, relevant, and fit for purpose across diverse research environments. The pilot phase involved structured testing in a representative sample of research-performing organisations (RPOs), including:

- Five universities: University of Oslo (UiO), University of Helsinki (UH), University of Tartu (UT), University of Latvia (UL), and University of Humanistic studies (UHS).
- One non-profit RPO: The European Network of Research Ethics Committees (EUREC).
- One national public RPO: The French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE).
- One private SME RPO: Trilateral Research Ltd. (TRI).

Figure 1. Pilot institutions.

By selecting these varied institutions, the task will ensure that the tools and materials are tested in diverse organisational settings, spanning public, private, non-profit, large and small RPOs, to capture a wide range of feedback and user needs.

The effectiveness of the pilot-tests has been systematically evaluated using some of the evaluation tools developed under WP4 (D 4.2- *Large-scale feasible measurement instruments on short, medium and long- term training effects adapted to the needs of a variety of target groups and different fields/ domains*) and during the pilot phase. These tools will assess factors such as user satisfaction, usability, relevance, and perceived impact of the materials and tools. Data collected through this evaluation will directly inform the refinement and optimisation of the outputs from T6.2 (*Devise a trainer guide to enhance training materials and tools developed by*

related projects) and T6.3 (*Develop new training materials and tools on RE/RI*), ensuring that the final versions respond to user needs and practical realities in research environments.

In addition, this deliverable describes the organization of online training sessions to further disseminate the materials and allow broader engagement from the research community. Researchers interested in improving their practices in line with the developed tools and materials have been able to register for these sessions. These sessions have been also used to gather feedback for the refinement of the materials. Therefore, the online sessions were integral part of the piloting phase. In the next session, this deliverable will give an overview of the pilot phase, including in-person and online sessions together. Then, it will give an overview only of the training sessions organized online.

2 Background

The BEYOND materials tested during the pilot phase have been produced in tasks 6.2 and 6.3 and are described in [D.6.2](#). The materials tested during the pilot phase can be found on ZENODO.

This deliverable reports on the pilot test of the materials and tools developed in task 6.2 and 6.3 and on the organization of online sessions.

The BEYOND Trainer Guide is a comprehensive resource designed for educators to promote integrity and ethical behaviour in research by teaching responsible conduct of research (RCR). It offers a detailed framework with practical tools and strategies for trainers to engage researchers in discussions, activities, and case studies, fostering deep understanding of ethical issues throughout the research process. The guide emphasizes critical thinking, ethical decision-making, and accountability, providing trainers with adaptable resources to effectively design and deliver impactful sessions tailored to various audiences, including students, early-career researchers, and experienced professionals.

The new training material developed by the project will focus on two specific target groups, each with their own set of RE and RI topics and are based on findings of BEYOND, especially on hitherto neglected topics such as mentoring, supervision and leadership. Materials on responsible mentoring, supervision and leadership are prepared for senior researchers and managers. Materials for the second target group – junior and early career researchers – are developed based on a gamification approach and focusing on topics identified during the earlier phases of BEYOND. All the material can be found on ZENODO:

- [The Trainer Guide](#)
- [Material on responsible mentoring, supervision and leadership](#)
- [Material for junior and early career researchers](#)

3 Pilot-testing

The pilot-testing phase aims to revise and refine the initial versions of the material developed by WP 6 and described in D6.2. The pilot-testing phase started in M 23 (October 2024) and lasted 12 months, until M 34 (October 2025). After revising and refining the educational resources created in BEYOND, all the material will be made fully accessible and available in ZENODO and The Embassy of Good Science Platform.

3.1 Methodology

The training materials were tested by eight pilot institutions, each engaging with them in different capacities based on their resources and ability to organize dedicated training sessions targeting specific stakeholder groups. The planning phase spanned the first two months of the pilot period. During this time, the pilot institutions carefully designed and scheduled their training activities, ensuring alignment with the project's overarching objectives. To facilitate systematic and methodologically sound collection of feedback, WP6 developed a dedicated methodology, drawing essential support from WP4, which focuses on methodologies to measure the effects of ethics and integrity training. As part of this process, tailored questionnaires and reporting templates were created to capture detailed information that could inform subsequent revisions of the training materials (see Attachments 1 and 2). The piloting of the materials officially commenced in January 2025, coinciding with the project's annual General Assembly held in Helsinki. The pilot-testing phase ended at the end of June, in order to give time to the developers of the material implement the feedback by revising the resources. The training material focusing on ECRs has been also tried out during the [ENRIO congress held in Ljubljana](#) during the workshop carried out on Wednesday, Sep 24, 2025, titled: Case-based approach for new and emerging issues in research ethics and integrity training.

A visual summary of the pilot phase is provided below.

Figure 2. Overview of the pilot phase process.

The figure illustrates the main stages of the pilot phase: (1) planning of pilot sessions by the pilot institutions, (2) piloting of the materials, (3) collection and analysis of feedback and (4) finalization of the training material. The process concludes with the revision of the training materials, informed by the feedback gathered throughout the pilot activities.

The pilot testing has been done in both in-person and online settings, depending on the capacity of the different institutions.

3.2 Pilot phase

The training materials developed by WP 6 have been piloted with more than 250 people (researchers at different career stages, supervisors, education experts) in both in-person and online settings (see the detailed table below). A total of 20 training sessions (12 in-person, 8 online) have been organized during the time of task 6.4 and feedback has been gathered for the refinement and finalization of the material. The pilot phase included the try-out of different training materials, mainly for early-career researchers, but also targeting supervisors and trainers across several institutions. The number of participants and sessions vary widely between institutions, reflecting differences in scale and scope of engagement. The table gives an overview of the in-person and online sessions, since both training settings were part of the pilot-testing process.

Institution	N of sessions (in-person and online)	Number of participants	Type of material piloted
UHS	2	13	ECRs
UiO	2	27	ECRs/ supervision
UT	3	58	ECRs
UH	3	57	Trainer guide/ ECRs/ supervision
UL	2	62	ECRs/ supervision
EUREC	4	56	ECRs
TRI	3	12	Trainer guide/ ECRs
INRAE	1	4	ECRs

Table 1. Overview of the training sessions during the pilot phase

The pilot-testing phase, which included the above-mentioned institutions, presents several important limitations. Specifically, three out of the eight institutions involved, EUREC, TRI, and INRAE, face significant constraints in organising dedicated training sessions to pilot the materials, as well as in recruiting participants such as master's students, PhD candidates, researchers, or other research stakeholders. This limitation stems from the fact that these institutions are not universities: EUREC is a non-profit research performing organisation (RPO), INRAE is a public RPO, and TRI is a private small- to medium-sized RPO. As such, they lack an internal pool of students or early-career researchers who could readily engage in piloting the BEYOND materials. This structural limitation reduces the breadth and diversity of feedback that can be gathered during the pilot phase, potentially affecting the representativeness and generalisability of the findings.

3.3. Feedback gathering

In order to collect feedback for the revision of the training materials developed in tasks 6.2 and 6.3 and piloted in task 6.4, WP6 developed a specific questionnaire to be shared with trainers (consortium members affiliated with the pilot institutions) and trainees after the training sessions (see attachments 7.1 and 7.2). Moreover, pilot-testing institutions submitted specific pilot reports to provide further feedback on the training materials (see example in attachment 7.3). The feedback gathered via the questionnaires and the pilot reports were fundamental for the revision of the training materials. In the next sessions, we will first report on the feedback related to the training material for ECRs and gathered via the questionnaire. Then, we will provide a summary of the feedback gathered via the pilot reports from the pilot institutions.

3.3.1. Report on feedback for training materials for early career researchers (questionnaire)

Between spring and summer 2025, 14 training sessions for early-career researchers were held — 6 in person and 8 online, with a total of 182 participants. The BEYOND training materials were piloted, and feedback was collected from two groups within the BEYOND research consortium:

- Early career researchers (students) who engaged with the cases and learning content.
- Trainers who introduced the method and materials and facilitated the sessions.

Feedback was collected via surveys distributed via QR-code focusing on the clarity of instructions, engagement of materials, and effectiveness in teaching research ethics and integrity (REI) themes. Open comments were also gathered as part of the survey.

According to IP address geolocation of feedback data originated from 11 countries, namely Estonia, Netherlands, Latvia, France, Spain, Norway, UK, Greece, Ireland, Italy, and Belgium.

3.3.1.1. Student feedback

From the 182 participants, a total of 68 responses were collected. Notably, only a small number of participants engaged with just a single case. The majority explored multiple cases, with some progressing through as many as 10 or 11. This indicates a high level of engagement with the training material and suggests that participants were motivated to explore different scenarios rather than limiting themselves to the minimum requirement.

Quantitative findings (on Likert scale):

Instructions were clear:

- Strongly agree: 37
- Agree: 30
- Neutral: 1

Training materials were engaging:

- Strongly agree: 30
- Agree: 35
- Neutral: 3

Training materials were effective:

- Agree: 30
- Strongly agree: 28
- Neutral: 8
- Disagree: 2

The feedback on clarity of instructions was overwhelmingly positive, the materials were found highly engaging with very few reservations and the effectiveness in teaching REI themes the majority found the materials effective, though a small group expressed doubts.

Qualitative Insights

Several positive remarks highlighted that the cases stimulated discussion. Some students expressed uncertainty about the clarity of the goal of the exercises. Questions arose regarding whether the objective was to select one correct option or to reach consensus on a solution. (For example: “Please make clear what the precise goal of the exercises is: to choose one from the four options. Also, what is the goal of the discussion?”)

Students also noted that case descriptions lacked sufficient detail, which made ethical decision-making challenging. More background information was requested to better understand the dilemmas. (For example “The only criticism I have is that I would like for the case to provide more information” and “Some cases were vague and lacked specifics. This could be intentional but also caused discussion about how to understand the case, rather than its contents.”)

Overall, students found the training engaging and thought-provoking. Discussions were especially rich in smaller groups, and the variety of cases and settings was appreciated. (For example: “Very good way of learning” and “I liked the variety in the cases and research settings.”)

Students offered several constructive suggestions to enhance the training experience. These included providing justifications for each option, showing statistics of peer choices, clarifying phrasing, and integrating ethical keywords into discussions. Minor issues were noted regarding formatting and presentation. These included typos, layout problems, and time constraints that limited the ability to discuss all cases.

3.3.1.2. Trainers feedback

Trainer from the pilot institutions responded to the questionnaire.

Quantitative findings (on Likert scale):

Number of responses: 9

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Quantitative findings (Likert scale)

Instructions were clear:

- Strongly agree: 4
- Agree: 4
- Neutral: 1

Training materials were engaging:

- Strongly agree: 3
- Agree: 5
- Neutral: 1

Training materials were effective:

- Strongly agree: 3
- Agree: 3
- Neutral: 2
- Disagree: 1

Overall the instructions designed for trainers were generally clear, though not unanimously. Materials were seen as engaging for students and the effectiveness of materials in delivering REI themes was mostly positive, though some trainers felt the REI learning outcomes were not fully achieved.

Qualitative Insights

Trainers reported that certain instructions were unclear, particularly in situations where the available choices were not mutually exclusive. This occasionally led to uncertainty about how participants were expected to proceed, suggesting a need for clearer guidance or restructuring of decision options. Despite these issues, trainers generally considered the materials highly engaging and effective. Engagement appeared to be especially strong when participants were allowed to select their own cases, which fostered a sense of ownership and relevance in the learning process. Overall, the interactive format was well received and seen as conducive to active learning.

Suggestions:

- To clarify ethical frameworks behind each option.
- To ensure dilemmas are morally complex and context-rich.
- To improve sequencing of slides and layout for online delivery.
- To consider adapting materials for different research environments (e.g., SMEs vs. universities).

3.3.2. Feedback provided by the pilot institutions via the pilot reports (summary)

The pilot report was created by WP 6 and the pilot institutions provided feedback on the pilot phase carried out and the training material developed. The pilot reports were gathered, analyzed and summarized. In the following session, a summary of the feedback is provided.

3.3.2.1. Feedback on the ECRs training material

The feedback regarding the ECR case-based training materials showed that the scenarios were engaging and stimulated meaningful, in-depth discussions on how to address research ethics challenges. They were also considered realistic, reflecting the kinds of dilemmas commonly encountered by researchers, particularly in academic settings. This was consistent with the learning aim of fostering critical ethical reflection and encouraging deliberation on managing ethics issues through practical cases. At the same time, some cases contained ambiguities or lacked sufficient detail, which made it harder for participants to make well-informed, context-sensitive decisions. The answer options offered could also be refined to capture more nuance and align more clearly with the four philosophical positions described in the guidance. From the perspective of subject matter experts, most case studies appeared to be tailored to academic research contexts, suggesting that the resource would benefit from adaptations or additional cases to increase its relevance for non-academic research environments. However, clearer instructions are needed, and some case-studies lack details when presenting the fictional cases

3.3.2.2. Feedback on the supervisor training material

The feedback regarding the supervision training materials showed strong overall effectiveness. Content was highly relevant for supervisors, though some elements, such as the REI leadership framework and ethical approaches tasks, could be simplified for clarity. Ethical principles were presented differently across posters, with Kitchener's principles proving particularly clear, though facilitators should retain flexibility in selecting which to use. The visual design of both slides and posters was praised for its appeal and structure, while clear poster instructions enabled productive discussions even without facilitator support. The Reflection Compass results showed that participants had a strong grasp of the topic and were highly engaged, demonstrating that the learning objectives were effectively met.

3.3.2.3. Feedback on the trainer guide

The Trainer Guide was found to be scientifically rigorous, offering a clear definition and classification of REI principles and types. A key strength is that it brings together a wide range of valuable RCR training resources into a single, accessible reference point. These qualities

make it a solid foundation for supporting research integrity training. While the guide could benefit from being more concise, clarifying its target audience, and improving navigation to help users find specific information more easily, it already provides a strong basis for further refinement. From the perspective of a subject matter expert, the guide demonstrates strong relevance to academic environments, offering thorough coverage in that domain. However, its impact could be broadened by adapting its content to better reflect the needs of non-academic research sectors, such as industry or governmental research settings. Overall, it serves as a robust foundation that is well-positioned for further development and wider applicability.

4 Online training sessions

T 6.4 included in its description that at least 5 online training should have been organized. Instead carrying out the online sessions separately from the pilot phase, we make the online training integral part of the piloting process. As we emphasised before, online training sessions were integral part of the pilot-testing phase. In total, 8 training sessions were organized online with a total of 116 participants.

Institution	Number of online sessions	Number of participants	Type of material
UT	1	17	ECRs
UL	1	34	ECRs/ supervision
EUREC	4	56	ECRs
TRI	2	9	ECRs

Table 2. Overview of the training sessions during the pilot phase

UT, UL, and TRI each organised online training sessions by engaging their in-house and international researchers, which allowed them to pilot the materials within their existing institutional communities. In contrast, EUREC, lacking an internal pool of researchers or students to draw upon, had to adopt a different approach. EUREC successfully conducted four online training sessions with international researchers, although it had originally planned to run five sessions. Unfortunately, one of the planned sessions had to be cancelled due to insufficient enrolment.

To recruit participants for these sessions, EUREC prepared and disseminated a detailed promotional leaflet, which was shared through multiple LinkedIn personal accounts as well as EUREC’s institutional LinkedIn account. While this approach helped attract a diverse international audience, the reliance on open online recruitment also introduced challenges in predicting participant numbers and ensuring consistent attendance across sessions. The

advertising material has also been shared by other EU-funded initiatives and by the members of the BEYOND SAB.

An extra online training session will be organized in collaboration with [NERQ](#) (SIG – early career researchers) and the EU-funded project [PATTERN](#) and [EARMA](#) on November 26th. This training aims to increase BEYOND training materials and BEYOND sustainability after the end of the project. The training session will include participation of early-career researcher, senior researchers, and research administrators with a specific interest in RI.

5 Revised versions of the BEYOND material

Following the pilot phase, the BEYOND training materials underwent a comprehensive revision process to incorporate feedback from both participants and facilitators. The pilot provided valuable insights into the clarity, relevance, and usability of the content, as well as the effectiveness of the proposed training methods. Based on these findings, the revision aimed not only to refine the structure and flow of the sessions, but also to enhance interactivity, contextual relevance, and accessibility. This process ensured that the final training materials more effectively support participants in developing the intended knowledge and skills, while also aligning with the broader objectives of the BEYOND project.

The revised training materials have been uploaded on ZENODO (see links to the training materials below), and will be uploaded to the online platform The Embassy of Good Science by the end of the project (End of December 2025).

- [The Trainer Guide](#)
- [Material on responsible mentoring, supervision and leadership](#)
- [Material for junior and early career researchers](#)

6 Conclusion

The pilot-testing phase has been a crucial step in ensuring that the BEYOND training materials are evidence-based, practical, and adaptable across diverse research environments. By engaging a wide range of research-performing organisations and gathering systematic feedback from both trainers and trainees, the consortium has been able to refine and optimise the materials to better address the needs of early-career researchers, supervisors, and trainers. While limitations in institutional capacity influenced the breadth of piloting in some settings, the process nonetheless generated valuable insights into usability, relevance, and impact. The revised training resources – including the Trainer Guide, materials on responsible mentoring, supervision and leadership, and gamified materials for early-career researchers – are now accessible on ZENODO and will be made available on the Embassy of Good Science platform by the end of the project. Together, these outputs represent a

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significant contribution to strengthening a culture of research ethics and integrity, equipping stakeholders with practical tools to prevent research misconduct, and fostering public trust in science.

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7 Attachments

7.1 Questionnaire to be shared with students

BEYOND research ethics and integrity training materials for young/early career researchers

Feedback form for STUDENTS

* Required

1. How many cases did you discuss? *

2. I thought: *

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
instructions were clear	<input type="radio"/>				
materials were engaging	<input type="radio"/>				
materials were effective in teaching key research ethics and integrity themes	<input type="radio"/>				

3. We very much welcome any other comments or suggestions, the materials are still in the piloting phase!

7.2 Questionnaire to be shared with instructors

BEYOND research ethics and integrity training materials for young/early career researchers

Feedback form for INSTRUCTORS

* Required

1. Thank you for helping us pilot and improve these materials.
How many cases did you use? *

2. Please respond to the following statements. I thought that: *

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
instructions were clear	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
materials were engaging for students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
materials were effective in delivering the key REI themes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3. Any comments on those issues:

4. Your comments on

- What facilitated the learning experience during the training?
- How would you rate your overall experience?
- Any other comments.

7.3 Pilot report questionnaire

Project Name:

Pilot Phase Conducted By:

Date of Report:

Training Material Tested:

1. Executive Summary

Provide a brief overview of the pilot phase, including key objectives, methods, participants, and major findings.

2. Methodology

2.1. Participants

- **Number of participants:**
- **Demographics:**

3.2. Pilot Format

- Duration and structure of the pilot (e.g., workshop, e-learning, blended format).
- Delivery platform (if applicable).
- Context and setting (e.g., university, organization, online).

4. Trainer Feedback

Summarize the feedback received regarding:

- **Content:** Relevance, accuracy, and clarity.
- **Design:** Visual appeal, structure, and ease of navigation.
- **Delivery:** Effectiveness of the format.
- **Learning Outcomes:** Achievement of learning goals and participant satisfaction.

5. Key Strengths and Challenges Identified

- **Strengths:** What worked well?
- **Challenges:** What issues or gaps were identified?

6. Recommendations for Improvement

Provide actionable suggestions for enhancing the training material based on the findings.

